

Histopathological Spectrum of Obstructive Lesions in Large Intestine in Tertiary Care Hospital in Haryana: A Prospective Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Intestinal obstruction (IO) disrupts normal intestinal content flow, affecting both small and large bowels. With rising global cancer cases, colorectal cancer (CRC) significantly contributes to morbidity, accounting for 10% of cancer incidences and deaths. Risk factors for CRC include dietary habits, sedentary lifestyle, and age, with higher rates in developed nations. Differentiating small and large bowel obstructions is crucial due to distinct clinical approaches. This study examines the histopathological spectrum of large bowel obstructive lesions in a tertiary care hospital, highlighting the critical role of histopathology in diagnosing and managing IO, especially in cases involving malignant transformations.

Material and Methods: This prospective study at BPS GMC examined resected specimens and endoscopic biopsies of large intestine obstructive lesions over one year. Following ethical approval and informed consent, samples were processed with H&E, histochemical, and IHC staining for histopathological analysis, excluding cases with perforation, poor preservation, or inadequate biopsies.

Results: The present study analysed 30 large intestine specimens, comprising 46.7% resections and 53.3% biopsies. Neoplastic lesions (70%) predominated, with adenocarcinoma (30%) being most common. A significant link was found between dietary patterns and lesion type ($p = 0.011$). The rectum was the most frequently affected site (53.3%).

Conclusion: The study underscores diverse histological variations in large intestine obstructions, emphasising multifactorial causes and significant impacts on young, active individuals.

Keywords: Adenocarcinoma, large intestine, obstruction.

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Introduction

Intestinal obstruction (IO) refers to any interruption, cessation or reversal of the normal passage of intestinal contents from the mouth to the anal canal. The obstruction may occur in either the small bowel or the large bowel. As per the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) predictions suggest that by 2050, there will be a dramatic increase in cancer cases worldwide, exceeding 35 million which marks a 77% rise from the estimated 20 million cases reported in 2022. [1]

According to Global Cancer Statistics 2020, colorectal cancer (CRC), including anal cancer, has a significant global impact with 1.9 million newly diagnosed cases and approximately 935,000 deaths. CRC is thus a substantial contributor to global cancer incidences and mortality, accounting for about 10% of all cancer cases and fatalities. [2] The risk factors for development of (CRC) encompass

dietary habits, a sedentary lifestyle and advancing age. Notably, developed nations exhibit higher incidence and mortality rates, likely associated with practices characterised by high fat and red meat consumption along with insufficient physical activity leading to obesity leading to fluctuations in mortality observed over time. [3]

Differentiating between small bowel obstruction and large bowel obstruction is essential due to variations in clinical presentation, evaluation, and treatment modalities. Moreover, conditions like intestinal pseudo-obstruction, such as Ogilvie's syndrome imitate symptoms of bowel obstruction. [4,5] Pathologists play a crucial role in diagnosis with histopathological confirmation serving as the gold standard, particularly for confirming malignancies. Colonoscopic biopsy is crucial in assessing large bowel diseases, highlighting the necessity for

constant correlation with clinical and endoscopic findings. Despite advancements an accurate interpretation remains an intriguing diagnostic challenge for pathologists due to the limited dimensions of the specimens. [6,7]

This article aims to explore the histopathological spectrum of obstructive lesions within the large intestine based on observation from a tertiary care hospital. By elucidating the intricate patterns and nuances of histological findings we seek to emphasize the essential role of histopathology in the prompt diagnosis and tailored management of IO, particularly in the context of malignant transformations. Through this comprehensive exploration, we aspire to contribute towards enhanced patient outcomes and a deeper understanding of this multifaceted clinical entity.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was conducted over a period of one year in the Department of Pathology, BPS GMC, Khanpur Kalan, and Sonapat. This study was undertaken after obtaining approval from Institutional ethical committee (reference-BPSGMCW/RC794/IEC/22 dated 11/10/2022) and written informed consent was secured from all participants prior to the study.

All resected specimens and endoscopic biopsies which were received for obstructive lesions of the large intestine in the department were included in the study, however cases of perforation without obstructive cause, poorly preserved specimens and inadequate biopsies were excluded from the study.

The resected specimens and endoscopic biopsies, received were fixed in 10% formalin overnight. The external and cut surface examination was performed and if the specimen was fresh, the mesentery was separated close to the intestinal wall for ease of examination and a longitudinal cut was made along the anti-mesenteric border as a standard procedure following adequate fixation, gross examination was conducted. Sections were paraffin-embedded followed by haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining were viewed under the microscope.

Additionally, histochemical and IHC staining were performed as needed with correlations drawn from findings of light microscopy.

Results

A one year prospective cross sectional study was conducted on 30 specimens comprising of 46.7% resected specimens and 53.3% endoscopic biopsies. Among the 30 specimens analysed, the cohort included 21 (70%) males and 09 (30%) females with age group ranging from 11 months to a maximum of 90 years. The distribution of neoplastic and non-neoplastic obstructive lesions in the large intestine based on dietary patterns with 10 cases(33.3%) in the non-vegetarian group and 20 cases (66.7%) in the vegetarian group. In the non-vegetarian group 100% cases were classified as neoplastic, while in the vegetarian group, 11 cases (55%) were neoplastic and 9 cases (45%) were non neoplastic. The chi square test results indicate a significant association between dietary patterns and the occurrence of neoplastic or non-neoplastic obstructive lesions in the large intestine (Chi- square = 6.429, p = 0.011) thus highlighting the potential relationship between diet and the nature of obstructive lesions in the large intestine.

In the present study, the most common site of involvement was rectum (53.3% cases) followed by ascending colon (13.3%cases). The patients presented most commonly with abdominal pain (63.3% cases) followed by constipation and rectal bleeding (53.3% cases) (table 1)

Out of 30 specimens included in the present study, 9 (30%) cases were of non-neoplastic lesions as depicted in figure below (figure 1) and 21 cases (70%) were of neoplastic lesions constituted by 6 (28.6%) benign entities comprising of 4 cases of juvenile rectal polyp and 1 case each of adenoma and fibroepithelial polyp. The neoplastic lesions consisted of 15 (71.4%) cases comprising of 10 cases of adenocarcinoma followed by 1 case each of germ cell tumor, metastasis, neuroendocrine tumor, and poorly differentiated malignant tumor and SCC anal canal.

There were 5 cases of moderately differentiated adenocarcinoma, 3 cases of well differentiated adenocarcinoma and 1 case each of mucin secreting and poorly differentiated adenocarcinoma. Our results indicate that adenocarcinoma (30%) was the commonest diagnosis followed by juvenile rectal polyp (13.3%) of all lesion involving large intestine.

Table 1: Distribution of symptoms in patients with large bowel obstruction.

Symptoms	No. of cases (n)	Percentage %
Abdominal Pain	19	63.33%
Constipation	16	53.33%
Rectal Bleeding	16	53.33
Vomiting	15	50%
Loss of Appetite	11	36.67%
Tenesmus	9	30%
Melena	9	30%

Mass Per Abdomen	7	23.33%
Fever	6	20%
Abdominal Distension	5	16.67%

- Amoebic enterocolitis
- Cloth fiber bezoar
- Colonic stricture
- Hirschsprung's Disease
- Ischemic colitis
- Reactive lymphadenitis
- Sigmoid volvulus

Figure 1: Distribution of non-neoplastic diseases in large bowel

Figure 2: (A) Amoebic Enterocolitis - Tissue Section Shows Trophozoites Of Entamoeba (H & E Stain X100) With (Inset) Exhibiting Pas-Positivity Depicted By Deep Pink Colour Along With Abundant Dense Cytoplasm And A Small Round Nucleus (Periodic Acid Schiff Stain, 400x) , 2 (B) Hirschsprung's Disease – Showing Hypertrophied Nerves Highlighted By S 100 With A Decreased Number Of Ganglion Cells (Immunohistochemistry, 400x)

Figure 3 (A) Juvenile rectal polyp - tissue section demonstrates an edematous lamina propria with an inflammatory infiltrate, cystically dilated glands lined by reactive epithelium and an accumulation of mucus and inflammatory debris within the glands. (H&E stain, 40X), 3 (B) Germ cell tumor exhibiting fibro adipose tissue admixed with atypical cells (H&E stain, 100X) with (inset) showing Yolk sac tumor component with Schiller -Duval body (H&E stain, 400X), 3 (C) Microphotograph shows the structure of the intestine with the interface of the normal intestine and malignant glands reaching beyond serosa (H&E stain, 100X), 3 (D) haphazardly arranged neoplastic glands of varying sizes with tumour cells showing high N: C ratio, loss of nuclear polarity and are surrounded by inflammatory and scattered congested vessels (H&E stain, 400X), (Inset) shows the tumor cells in adenocarcinoma showing positivity for CK 19 (Immunohistochemistry, 400X)

Discussion

Large bowel obstruction is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality, arising from various etiologies including hernia, tumor, adhesions or issues with biochemical imbalances. It is among the most common and potentially life threatening intra-abdominal emergency challenge that general surgeons face. Patients typically present with acute abdominal symptoms often requiring intestinal resection. Studies indicate that acute abdominal cases account for 20-40% of emergency surgical admissions. In our study, most of the cases (n=17; 56.6%) involved young and middle age people with the majority being under 50 years of age with the mean age being 36.96 ± 23.95 years. Similar findings regarding the age distribution of IO have been reported in studies by Yusuf NW et al [8], Kirar D et al [9] and Alegbeleye BJ et al [7]. Out of the 30 study subjects, 21 were male and 9 were females, however no significant correlation between gender and the site of obstructive intesti-

nal lesions was found in the present study. Studies from various regions worldwide including Shukla S et al [10], Tiwari SJ et al [11] and Jiang W et al [12] have consistently shown a higher prevalence of IO in males compared to females. The gender gap could stem from sociocultural norms and limited healthcare access for rural women confined to domestic roles which may also limit their exposure to certain infections.

In the present study, abdominal discomfort was the most commonly reported symptom. This finding mirrors the observations documented in studies conducted by Shukla S et al [10] and Tiwari SJ et al [11]. A statistically significant correlation was noted between the sites of obstruction and specific symptoms, including abdominal pain ($p = 0.001$), rectal bleeding ($p = 0.001$) and constipation ($p = 0.049$). These results explain the differences in symptoms between the small bowel obstruction and large bowel obstruction. Unlike many other studies that focus solely on acute IO, the present study also

included chronic and subacute cases. Hirschsprung's disease was the predominant congenital anomaly in the large intestine representing 100% of cases in this category. Masgal M et al [13] reported cases of Meckel's diverticulum and Hirschsprung's disease, among congenital anomalies causing IO in their study. Infectious causes, particularly amoebic enterocolitis accounted for 11% of cases in the large intestine. Amoebic colitis presenting as subacute IO was reported by Verma R et al [14] in a case report. Additionally, colonic strictures and sigmoid volvulus were exclusively found in the large intestine.

These findings emphasize the differential distribution of non neoplastic intestinal pathologies between the small intestine and large intestine, highlighting the significance of anatomical consideration in diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. In the present study, histomorphological analysis indicated the malignant lesions were the most frequently diagnosed among the 30 specimens surpassing benign lesions.

The data analysis revealed a statistically significant correlation between the neoplastic lesions and the site of obstructive intestinal lesions, with a chi-square value of 25.754 and a p-value of 0.041. Notable malignant lesions include adenocarcinoma, germ cell tumor, neuroendocrine tumor, metastatic deposits in the omentum, poorly differentiated malignant tumor and SCC of the anal canal. These findings highlighted the varied nature of malignant entities contributing to obstructive lesions within the GI tract.

A study by Jiang W et al [12] reported a significantly higher percentage of malignancies with 96.43 % and 3.57 % were reported as benign. Adenocarcinoma emerged as the most common lesion in this study, consisting of 33.3% of total cases, consistent with findings from Kirar D et al [9]. However, study conducted by Yusuf et al [8] in 2014 indicated that strictures were the leading cause of IO. Clinical studies by Jena SS et al [15] and Valarmathi M et al [16] identified adhesive obstruction as the predominant cause of IO.

In the present study, adenocarcinoma was predominantly observed in the majority of case with rectum being the most common site (53.3%), followed by the the ascending colon (13.3%). The distribution of adenocarcinoma in the current study aligns with some previous research conducted by Sulegaon R et al [17], and Kirar D et al [9]. Biopsy specimens were more common (60%) than resection specimens (40%) among the adenocarcinoma cases. This highlighted the importance of rectal biopsy for the early diagnosis of malignant lesions of the large colon. Early presentation of carcinoma cases can be attributed to increased awareness, easy accessibility to good medical facilities, and diag-

nostic resources like endoscopic biopsies available at tertiary care hospitals in rural areas.

Conclusion

The present study highlights the landscape of obstructive lesions within the large intestine are characterized by diverse histological variations and intricate clinical manifestations. It emphasizes the importance of considering multifactorial aetiologies such as age, gender, dietary habits, and addiction history in their etiology and management. Notably, a significant proportion of cases affect young, economically active individuals, thereby illustrating the considerable impact of bowel obstruction on productivity and quality of life.

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